

Pre-Budget 2027 Submission

The design architecture of digitised welfare formulas and the reliability of Budget 2027 expenditure projections

To: Joint Committee on Social Protection, Rural and Community Development, Houses of the Oireachtas (34th Dáil, 27th Seanad)

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Executive summary

As Ireland digitises its benefit and means-test formulas, how those formulas are disclosed will determine whether Budget 2027 expenditure projections are reliable and whether automated decisions respect claimants' rights. Two governments have already shown what goes wrong at the extremes: Kazakhstan published a deterministic, uncapped, unverified earnings-linked benefit formula and saw it gamed into a 320-billion-tenge fund deficit; the Netherlands ran an opaque fraud-scoring model that wrongly accused some 26,000 parents and helped bring down a government. The shared error was treating transparency as a single dial rather than a design space that must be calibrated by system type.

The core conclusion is that the budget-safe and rights-consistent answer is not maximal disclosure and not secrecy, but calibrated transparency: statutory rates and the right to a reasoned, appealable decision stay fully public, while gaming is contained through sound parametric design and income verification for benefit formulas, and through audit-only access for fraud-detection models. Ireland is well placed (its Pay-Related Benefit is capped and built on real-time PAYE data), so the live risk lies less there than in the means-test reform now under way. The incoming EU AI Act does not close the gap because a deterministic benefit formula is not an "AI system" within its definition.

In summary, the submission invites the Committee to recommend that the Department of Social Protection:

1. treat formula disclosure as a budgetary risk control, with adversarial pre-deployment testing before any formula is digitised;
2. calibrate disclosure by class of system, keeping statutory rates and thresholds fully public;
3. run an internal mutability audit of any fraud or risk-scoring model before deployment;
4. give the continuing calibration function to existing oversight bodies rather than a new one; and
5. not assume the EU AI Act closes this gap, and task the relevant Irish bodies with it.

Introduction

When a government digitises the formula that decides a welfare payment, it makes a design choice that determines whether the budget built on that payment is reliable. Publish a deterministic benefit formula in full, and it becomes an instruction manual for legal optimisation at population scale. Conceal the logic of a fraud-detection system, and it becomes a machine for unaccountable error. Two governments have already paid for the opposite halves of this single design error: one in billions, the other in the fall of a cabinet. Ireland, now legislating earnings-linked benefits, reforming the means test and preparing to digitise both, is making the same design choices.

This submission brings comparative international evidence to bear on one question that the Committee's own recommendations raise but do not resolve: not what the social welfare rates should be, but how the formulas that set them should be disclosed. The author's expertise is in enterprise architecture and the security of large public-sector systems; the design of disclosure interfaces is the subject of that field. The matter falls squarely within the Committee's remit because the reliability of income-support expenditure projections and the fundamental-rights exposure of automated benefit decisions are questions of budgetary design rather than technical detail. No individual case is raised.

Sources and approach

The analysis is comparative and doctrinal, not empirical. It examines two documented national cases that sit at the extreme ends of a single transparency spectrum: Kazakhstan (2024–2025) and the Netherlands (2013–2021), selected because each represents the opposite failure mode of the same design assumption. The evidence is drawn from primary public sources: national legislation, a court judgment, a parliamentary inquiry report, and ministry documents. These are read against the Irish design context as set out in the Department of Social Protection's recent instruments (2024–2025) and the European Union's Artificial Intelligence Act. The analytical framework draws on two of the author's working papers, cited below. No Irish administrative microdata were used; the submission does not claim to describe current Irish outcomes, but to inform forthcoming Irish design choices.

1. Two governments, the same error, two different systems

It is tempting to read the two cases below as foreign curiosities: a post-Soviet republic that lost control of its budget, and a continental administration that mistreated its citizens. That reading is the error this submission asks the Committee to resist. The two governments could hardly be more different in their political systems, administrative capacity, welfare traditions, or levels of development. Yet both made the same conceptual error – treating transparency as a single dial to be turned up or down, rather than as a multi-dimensional design space to be calibrated – in two different classes of system. Kazakhstan over-disclosed a deterministic benefit-entitlement formula; the Netherlands under-disclosed a probabilistic fraud-risk classifier. That the same error surfaces in such different systems is the point: it is why calibration must be specific to the type of system, as Section 4 sets out. The failures are not symmetrical in their politics, either – gaming imposes diffuse fiscal costs that a government can manage, while discrimination imposes concentrated harms that can bring a government down, which is precisely why the cheaper-looking over-disclosure error is the easier one to walk into.

Because the error is structural rather than local, it does not respect borders or institutional maturity. A jurisdiction that is mid-way through digitising its benefit formulas is not insulated from it by the quality of its civil service or the strength of its rights culture. Ireland is

precisely such a jurisdiction. The value of the two cases is that they convert a prospective design risk into a documented cost, in both directions, before Ireland incurs either.

2. Kazakhstan: the cost of maximum transparency

Kazakhstan calculates earnings-linked maternity and childcare benefits through an explicit, deterministic formula codified in its Social Code and published in full: average declared income over a reference period, multiplied by a coefficient, subject to a statutory ceiling (Parliament of Kazakhstan, 2023, Articles 78 and 85). Publication was not an oversight; it was consistent with the country's Law on Access to Information, which obliges agencies to publish the rules governing public services (Parliament of Kazakhstan, 2015).

The published formula functioned as an instruction manual. Because the benefit was tied to declared pre-leave earnings, the optimal strategy was to register nominal high-salary employment in the months before a claim, inflating the earnings base toward the ceiling. Accountants and social-media channels disseminated the method at the speed of digital communication. The Ministry of Labour and Social Protection reported that in 2024 the State Social Insurance Fund disbursed 958.3 billion tenge in benefits against 637.5 billion tenge in contributions – a gap of 320 billion tenge – with more than 82 per cent of expenditure (790 billion tenge) directed to maternity and childcare support, and its actuarial assessment projecting that the fund would reach insolvency as early as 2028 absent reform (Ministry of Labour and Social Protection of the Population, 2025a, c). The imbalance was concentrated regionally: in 15 regions, payouts exceeded contributions by a factor of 3.6 in Turkestan oblast and 2.7 in Zhambyl oblast, as stated by the Minister for Labour and Social Protection and reported by Kazakhstan media (Zakon.kz, 2025; Orda.kz, 2025). After a public clarification campaign, more than 2,000 recipients voluntarily acknowledged inflated income declarations, preventing an estimated 4.7 billion tenge in losses to the fund (Ministry of Labour and Social Protection of the Population, 2025c) – a revealing admission that the behaviour was optimisation within the rules, not fraud against them. The government responded with parameter-level caps (Ministry of Labour and Social Protection of the Population, 2025b), but the underlying architecture – a deterministic formula published in full – remains, and the new parameters are subject to the same dynamic.

The decisive point for a budget committee is this: the law, followed faithfully, acted against the interest it was designed to serve. Expenditure projections built on the assumption that

claimants would behave cooperatively were not merely optimistic; they were structurally wrong, because the published formula rewarded the opposite behaviour.

3. The Netherlands: the cost of minimum transparency

The Netherlands made the opposite error in two connected episodes. In the first, the tax authorities operated a self-learning "risk classification model" that scored childcare-benefit claims for fraud risk. Its logic was undisclosed, and applicants were neither told their risk scores nor given reasons. Between 2013 and 2019, as many as 26,000 parents were wrongly accused of childcare-benefit fraud (Henley, 2021; House of Representatives of the States General, 2020); the risk profiles drew on indicators correlated with nationality and ethnicity, directing suspicion at immigrant communities (Amnesty International, 2021). Families were classified as having acted with "malice or gross negligence" and subjected to an "all-or-nothing" recovery regime that disqualified them from graduated repayment and locked them out of other support; the cascading consequences included job loss, family breakdown and, in some cases, removal of children (House of Representatives of the States General, 2020). After the parliamentary inquiry's report *Unprecedented Injustice*, the government of Prime Minister Rutte resigned in January 2021 (Henley, 2021).

The second episode established the principle in law. The System Risk Indication (SyRI) was a separate government instrument that linked data across departments to flag residents for fraud investigation. In February 2020, the District Court of The Hague held that the SyRI legislation breached Article 8 of the European Convention on Human Rights: its application was "insufficiently transparent and verifiable", and it did not strike the fair balance that Article 8(2) requires (NJCM and others v. The State of the Netherlands (SyRI), 2020).

The anti-gaming defence offered for such opacity proved hollow. The indicators that attract concern in these systems (nationality, native language) are immutable; a person cannot strategically change them to evade detection. Where an indicator cannot be gamed, secrecy serves no protective purpose; it only removes the contestability that the court found to be a fundamental-rights requirement.

4. The common error: transparency is not a single dial

The two cases expose a distinction that policy discourse and most regulatory drafting conflate. Transparency is not one quantity but at least three (Shabad, 2026a, b):

- **Decision transparency** explains to an individual why their case produced its outcome. It is essential: it sustains appeals and is required for lawful, contestable administration. At the individual level, the gaming risk is low because one person's explanation does not aggregate into a population-level strategy.
- **Mechanical transparency** publishes the formula itself – the weights, thresholds and coefficients. At the population scale, this is a reverse-engineering interface: it lets strategic actors compute the optimal declaration, as Kazakhstan demonstrates.
- **Audit transparency** gives oversight bodies (auditors, an ombudsman, the courts) verifiable access to the system's logic without publishing it to the whole population. It delivers the accountability the Netherlands lacked, without creating the interface Kazakhstan exposed.

Kazakhstan provided maximum mechanical transparency where calibrated audit access would have preserved accountability at far lower fiscal risk. The Netherlands provided zero decision transparency where it was both legally required and practically essential. The shared root cause is the assumption that "more transparency" and "less transparency" are the only available moves. A further dynamic compounds the risk: governments amend rules through legislation over months or years, while populations share optimisation strategies within days. Any single transparency setting, however well-judged at launch, degrades as the population learns. Calibration is therefore not a one-off design decision but a continuing governance function.

5. The incoming EU AI Act does not close this gap

It would be reasonable for the Committee to assume that the European Union's Artificial Intelligence Act, whose high-risk obligations for "access to essential public services and benefits" take effect from 2 August 2026, will govern this risk. For one half of it, it does; for the more fiscally dangerous half, it does not.

The Act's high-risk safeguards attach to an "AI system". By Recital 12 of the Artificial Intelligence Act (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2024), that definition expressly excludes "systems that are based on the rules defined solely by natural persons to automatically execute operations"; the European Commission's guidance (European Commission, 2025) confirms that deterministic rule-based software and classical heuristics fall outside it. A means-test or benefit formula (the Kazakhstan artefact) is exactly such a deterministic, human-defined rule system. It is therefore not an "AI system" at all, and the high-risk regime does not reach it. By contrast, a machine-learning fraud-detection model (the Netherlands artefact) is captured as high-risk under Annex III(5)(a).

The result is a gap between laws. The instruments that mandate disclosure – freedom-of-information and open-government duties, the right to an explanation of automated decisions, and the administrative duty to give reasons – all push towards publishing the benefit formula. The instrument that might be expected to manage the resulting risk, the AI Act, is structurally blind to it because the gameable artefact is a deterministic formula it defines away. No instrument requires that mechanical disclosure be calibrated to the gaming and fiscal-sustainability risk it creates, and none assigns that task to anyone. The same proportionality principle that struck down SyRI cuts in both directions: uncalibrated opacity breaches the right to contest, and uncalibrated disclosure depletes the fund from which the entitlement is paid – defeating, in Kazakhstan's words, the interest the law exists to protect. Proportionality requires calibration; at present, no instrument supplies it.

The foundational instruments do not merely permit such calibration; they point towards it. Welfare benefits are protected possessions under Article 1 of Protocol No. 1 to the European Convention on Human Rights (*Stec and others v. the United Kingdom*, 2006), and the State's task under the Convention is to strike a fair balance between the general interest of the community and the rights of the individual (*Sporrong and Lönnroth v. Sweden*, 1982), with wide latitude in matters of social and economic policy. That general interest plainly includes a solvent fund and the equal treatment of the contributors who finance it. A configuration in which well-advised claimants secure an advantage contrary to the scheme's purpose, at the expense of honest contributors, is the kind of abuse of formally lawful rules that European law has long treated as unprotected (*Halifax plc and Others v. Commissioners of Customs and Excise*, 2006). None of this touches the individual's right to a reasoned, contestable decision, which remains non-negotiable; it bears only on how much of the underlying

mechanism is published to the population at large. The question is therefore not how much to disclose, but which configuration best discharges the State's duty to all its citizens at once.

6. Why this matters for Budget 2027: Ireland is making both choices now

Ireland is not contemplating these design choices in the abstract. It is making them on both dials during the period this Budget covers.

On the disclosure dial, the State has introduced Pay-Related Jobseeker's Benefit, payable from 31 March 2025 at 60 per cent of previous earnings (capped at €450), then 55 per cent and 50 per cent over a total of nine months (Department of Social Protection, 2024b). This is Ireland's first major working-age benefit tied to prior earnings, the same class of benefit Kazakhstan published and saw gamed. Ireland's design, however, is far better protected against the Kazakhstan failure than the bare comparison suggests, and it is worth saying so plainly. The benefit is capped (€450, then €375, then €300) and time-limited; entitlement depends on contribution history; and the earnings used are drawn from the Revenue Commissioners' real-time PAYE data for a fixed governing contribution year, not from earnings declared just before a claim. A claimant, therefore, cannot inflate the base on the eve of a claim; they would have had to overpay tax and contributions on a fictitious salary for a year or more in advance, for a benefit that is capped in any case. This is why earnings-related benefits across the EU have not produced Kazakhstan-scale gaming: the containment comes from the design parameters and from income verification, not from keeping the formula secret. Kazakhstan therefore shows the *type* of risk, not its scale; the lesson for Ireland is that the safeguard is good design, and the live design question lies less in Pay-Related Benefit than in the means test. The means-test formulas, income disregards and tapers are published openly, and they bite hardest on income that is not captured by real-time PAYE: self-employment, proprietary directors, asset valuation, and the treatment of multiple or seasonal employments. This is precisely the surface the Committee's own 2024 report on Means Testing in the Social Welfare System proposes to reform, recommending that the means test be simplified and streamlined so that information from one means test can be used when means testing is required for another payment (Joint Committee on Social Protection, 2024a), and its pre-budget submission recommended benchmarking core rates to a minimum essential standard of living and significant means-test reform (Joint Committee on Social Protection,

2024b). Benchmarking welfare rates to a share of average earnings – the approach the Roadmap for Social Inclusion already adopts for the State pension through a smoothed-earnings benchmark (Government of Ireland, 2020) – is itself a deterministic uprating formula that the aggregate expenditure line depends on. Each of these sits on the over-transparency dial, and each is a design choice made during the period this Budget covers.

On the opacity dial, the Department of Social Protection already runs opaque digital control systems – data analytics, facial-image matching and extensive data-matching (Department of Social Protection, 2025, 2024a). These are the Irish analogue of the Netherlands risk-classifier, and they have already drawn a fundamental-rights finding: in June 2025, the Data Protection Commission fined the Department €550,000 (RTE, 2025), finding that it had not established a valid legal basis for collecting facial-biometric data for the Public Services Card and had failed to give data subjects suitably transparent information (a decision the Department is contesting). The sum is small beside the Netherlands and Kazakhstan figures, and the finding concerns biometric data rather than fraud scoring, but it shows that opaque, rights-sensitive digital systems are already live in the Department that will administer any reformed means test. Budget 2027 design decisions on both dials will land precisely as the EU AI Act's high-risk regime activates.

7. A way through: calibrated transparency by design

The constructive principle is not to choose opacity over transparency, nor the reverse. It is to *calibrate* – and calibration works differently for the two classes of systems, which a constraint of legality keeps distinct. The rates, bands and thresholds of a statutory benefit must be public: the principle that the law be knowable, the requirement of legal certainty, and the right to an effective remedy all demand that a claimant can see the rule that decides their entitlement. So, for benefit-calculation formulas, the answer to gaming is not secrecy at all; it is sound parametric design – caps, ceilings, fixed or longer reference periods, anti-spike rules – backed by real-time income verification and tested by adversarial modelling before launch. Kazakhstan's failure was not that it published the formula; it was that it published a formula with no cap and no verification. For fraud-detection and risk-scoring models, the calculus differs because the operational weights of a risk model are not a statutory entitlement that anyone has a right to see. Here, the right setting is audit transparency: verifiable access for oversight bodies, without publishing the live model to the population. Across both classes,

decision transparency is preserved for every individual; only the population-scale disclosure of operational details is calibrated. The aim is not a single optimal setting – there is none, and the right balance differs by benefit type and risk context – but to map the trade-offs and deliver that decision space to political leaders, so that the choice between accountability, integrity and cost is made knowingly by those answerable for it, rather than defaulting silently to maximum disclosure. This is the bounded-explainability principle developed in the author's work (Shabad, 2026b): keep the decision logic fully deterministic, auditable and individually explained, while treating the population-scale disclosure of gameable operational detail as a design variable rather than an all-or-nothing choice.

Recommendations

The Committee is invited to recommend to the Department of Social Protection, in its Pre-Budget Submission report, the following. They are specific by design.

1. **Treat formula disclosure as a budgetary risk control.** Before any earnings-linked or means-tested formula is digitised (the Pay-Related Benefit reference-period rules, and any reformed means test) require an adversarial pre-deployment assessment that models how a population of strategic claimants, not cooperative applicants, would optimise declared inputs under full formula disclosure, and that estimates the resulting fiscal exposure. Budget 2027 expenditure projections for any such payment should state the transparency configuration assumed. A projection that assumes cooperative behaviour under a fully published deterministic formula systematically understates cost.
2. **Calibrate disclosure by class of system, within the constraint of legality.** The statutory rates, bands and thresholds of every benefit must remain fully public; nothing here suggests otherwise. The calibration applies only to two things: the operational detail of fraud and risk-scoring models, and the implementation specifics of genuinely gameable benefit parameters. For benefit-calculation formulas, the defence against gaming is parametric design and income verification, not concealment; for risk-scoring models, audit transparency – verifiable access for the Comptroller and Auditor General, the Ombudsman and the courts – delivers oversight without publishing an exploitable model to the population.

3. **For fraud-detection and risk-scoring, run an internal mutability audit before deployment.** As an audit-transparency check – not a publication requirement – requires documented evidence, before deployment, that the model does not rest on immutable or discriminatory indicators (nationality, native language, family structure). Such indicators cannot be gamed, so secrecy gives no anti-fraud benefit; what it removes is the contestability that the Netherlands case shows is a fundamental-rights requirement. This audit does not entail publishing live risk weights, which would allow strategic actors to evade the mutable indicators that a fraud model legitimately uses.
4. **Give the calibration function to existing oversight bodies, not a new one.** Gaming strategies emerge within implementation cycles faster than legislation can respond, so calibration must be continuous – but it need not mean a new body. The fiscal-sustainability aspect fits the Comptroller and Auditor General; the rights-and-bias aspect fits the Irish Human Rights and Equality Commission and the Data Protection Commission; and the interface with the EU AI Act fits the forthcoming National AI Office. What matters is that the monitoring and adjustment of disclosure formats are carried out by a body independent of the Department that administers the payment, for the same reason that fiscal oversight sits outside the spending department.
5. **Do not assume the EU AI Act closes this gap.** Because the high-risk obligations of Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 attach to "AI systems" and, by Recital 12, exclude systems based on rules defined solely by natural persons, a deterministic benefit formula falls outside them, while open-government and explanation duties continue to push towards its disclosure. Ireland's AI Act transposition arrangements and the forthcoming National AI Office should be explicitly tasked with calibrating mechanical transparency for deterministic public-benefit formulas, a task that no current instrument currently performs.

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Declarations

Use of artificial intelligence: During the preparation of this submission, the author used Claude (Anthropic) to improve readability and language quality as a non-native English speaker. After using this tool, the author reviewed and edited the content and takes full responsibility for the content of this submission.

Competing interests: For transparency, the author discloses that he practises as an independent governance advisor in algorithmic and data governance, the subject matter of this submission. He therefore has a professional interest in the adoption of calibrated transparency as a governance approach, as it aligns with his advisory practice. He has no financial interest in the specific outcome of this consultation; the submission is made in a personal capacity and in the public interest, and any assistance offered to the Committee or the Department would be provided on a pro bono basis. The author is the sole author of the working papers cited herein.